

Datum 2022-10-30

Dnr 2021-3125

Fyndnr.

Löpnr:

Handläggare: Elyse Canosa

SEM-EDS Instrument Report

Sample Identification Code

RAÄ Dnr 2021-3125 Object no. suffix

Samples

Type reference material art object/artifact

Form paint flakes from models (unaged and aged) of painting (Konstnärnförbundets styrelse, by Richard Bergh)

Colour various

Age new made

Material oil paint on Canvas

Concentrations N/A

Point of analysis See specific points of analysis for the different samples below.

Sample/Object	#	specifics
Un-aged canvas	UA3C1	w Zn white
	UA3C2	w/o Zn white
	UA1CB	w/o Zn white
Aged canvas	A3C1	w Zn white
	A3C2	w/o Zn white
	A1CB	w/o Zn white

Purpose

To investigate if and how the ageing conditions have induced soap formation within the paint layers, especially the models based on Zn-white.

Method

Sample preparation See 'Provtagningsprotokoll', samples embedded in Technovit® 2000 LC. Samples sputtered with 6 nm Au.

Sputter coating

SEM coating unit PS3 (Agar Scientific); City Country

Agar turbo carbon coater; City, Country

Gold carbon

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Org.nr 202100-1090

Plusgiro 59994-4

Bankgiro 5052-3620

Sputter time: 5 minutes
Sputter current: 20 mA
Terminate thickness: 6 nm

Instrument Parameters

JEOL JSM-IT500

Filament: tungsten

EHT: See photos below (in kV)

I probe: See photos below

Working Distance 10 mm

Magnification see photos below

Vacuum mode VP HP

Detector BS SE VPSE

Results

Sample UA3C1

Signal SED
Landing Voltage 15.0 kV
WD 10.1 mm
Magnification x200
F.O.V. 640.0 x 480.0 μm
Probe Current High 50.0
Scan Rotation 0.0°
Vacuum Mode HighVacuum

100 μm

100 µm

Signal BED-S
Landing Voltage 15.0 kV
WD 10.1 mm
Magnification x200
F.O.V. 640.0 x 480.0 µm
Probe Current High 50.0
Scan Rotation 0.0°
Vacuum Mode HighVacuum

50 µm

Signal BED-S
Landing Voltage 15.0 kV
WD 10.2 mm
Magnification x400
F.O.V. 320.0 x 240.0 µm
Probe Current High 50.0
Scan Rotation 0.0°
Vacuum Mode HighVacuum

Sample UA3C2

Signal BED-S
Landing Voltage 30.0 kV
WD 10.2 mm
Magnification x200
F.O.V. 640.0 x 480.0 μm
Probe Current High 50.0
Scan Rotation 0.0°
Vacuum Mode HighVacuum

100 μm

IMG1(1st)

IMG1

C-K

O-K

Mg-K

Al-K

Si-K

Ca-K

Ti-K

Cr-K

Zn-K

Pb-M

Sample UA1CB

Signal SED
Landing Voltage 15.0 kV
WD 10.3 mm
Magnification x200
F.O.V. 640.0 x 480.0 µm
Probe Current High 50.0
Scan Rotation 0.0°
Vacuum Mode HighVacuum

Signal BED-S
Landing Voltage 15.0 kV
WD 10.3 mm
Magnification x200
F.O.V. 640.0 x 480.0 μm
Probe Current High 50.0
Scan Rotation 0.0°
Vacuum Mode HighVacuum

100 μm

IMG1(1st)

IMG1

C-K

O-K

Na-K

Mg-K

Al-K

Si-K

Ca-K

Ti-K

Cr-K

Co-K

Sample A3C1

Signal SED
 Landing Voltage 15.0 kV
 WD 10.7 mm
 Magnification x200
 F.O.V. 640.0 x 480.0 µm
 Probe Current High 50.0
 Scan Rotation 0.0°
 Vacuum Mode HighVacuum

100 µm

100 μm

Signal BED-S
Landing Voltage 15.0 kV
WD 10.7 mm
Magnification x200
F.O.V. 640.0 x 480.0 μm
Probe Current High 50.0
Scan Rotation 0.0°
Vacuum Mode HighVacuum

50 μm

Signal BED-S
Landing Voltage 15.0 kV
WD 10.7 mm
Magnification x500
F.O.V. 256.0 x 192.0 μm
Probe Current High 50.0
Scan Rotation 0.0°
Vacuum Mode HighVacuum

Sample A3C2

Signal SED
Landing Voltage 15.0 kV
WD 11.8 mm
Magnification x200
F.O.V. 640.0 x 480.0 μm
Probe Current High 50.0
Scan Rotation 0.0°
Vacuum Mode HighVacuum

100 μm

Signal BED-S
Landing Voltage 15.0 kV
WD 11.8 mm
Magnification x200
F.O.V. 640.0 x 480.0 μm
Probe Current High 50.0
Scan Rotation 0.0°
Vacuum Mode HighVacuum

100 μm

Signal BED-S
 Landing Voltage 15.0 kV
 WD 11.7 mm
 Magnification x400
 F.O.V. 320.0 x 240.0 µm
 Probe Current High 50.0
 Scan Rotation 0.0°
 Vacuum Mode HighVacuum

50 µm

Sample A1CB

Signal SED
Landing Voltage 15.0 kV
WD 10.1 mm
Magnification x200
F.O.V. 640.0 x 480.0 μm
Probe Current High 50.0
Scan Rotation 0.0°
Vacuum Mode HighVacuum

100 μm

Signal BED-S
Landing Voltage 15.0 kV
WD 10.1 mm
Magnification x200
F.O.V. 640.0 x 480.0 μm
Probe Current High 50.0
Scan Rotation 0.0°
Vacuum Mode HighVacuum

100 μm

Signal BED-S
Landing Voltage 15.0 kV
WD 10.1 mm
Magnification x400
F.O.V. 320.0 x 240.0 μm
Probe Current High 50.0
Scan Rotation 0.0°
Vacuum Mode HighVacuum

50 μm

